

Combining Loop and Thiazide Diuretics Across the Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction Spectrum: The CLOROTIC Trial

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Abstract

Background

The addition of [hydrochlorothiazide](#) (HCTZ) to [furosemide](#) in the CLOROTIC (Combining Loop with [Thiazide Diuretics](#) for Decompensated Heart Failure) trial improved the [diuretic](#) response in patients with [acute heart failure](#) (AHF).

Objectives

This work aimed to evaluate if these results differ across the spectrum of [left ventricular ejection fraction](#) (LVEF).

Methods

This [post hoc analysis](#) of the randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled CLOROTIC trial enrolled 230 patients with AHF to receive either HCTZ or a placebo in addition to an intravenous [furosemide](#) regimen. The influence of LVEF on primary and secondary outcomes was evaluated.

Results

The median LVEF was 55%: 166 (72%) patients had LVEF >40%, and 64 (28%) had LVEF ≤40%. Patients with a lower LVEF were younger, more likely to be male, had a higher prevalence of [ischemic heart disease](#), and had higher [natriuretic peptide](#) levels. The addition of HCTZ to [furosemide](#) was associated with the greatest weight loss at 72 of 96 hours, better metrics of [diuretic](#) response, and greater 24-hour [diuresis](#) compared with placebo, with no significant differences according to the LVEF category (using 2 LVEF cutoff points: 40% and 50%) or LVEF as a continuous variable (all *P* values were insignificant). There were no significant differences observed with the addition of HCTZ in terms of mortality, rehospitalizations, or safety endpoints (impaired renal function, [hyponatremia](#), and hypokalemia) among the 2 LVEF groups (all *P* values were insignificant).

Conclusions

Adding HCTZ to intravenous [furosemide](#) seems to be effective strategy for improving [diuretic](#) response in AHF without treatment effect modification according to baseline LVEF. (Combining Loop with [Thiazide Diuretics](#) for Decompensated Heart Failure [CLOROTIC], [NCT01647932](#); Randomized, double blinded, multicenter study, to asses Safety and Efficacy of the Combination of Loop With Thiazide-type Diuretics vs [Loop diuretics](#) with placebo in Patients With Decompensated, EudraCT Number [2013-001852-36](#))

CENTRAL ILLUSTRATION: The CLOROTIC Trial Results According to LVEF

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